

ON MEMORY AND FORGETTING: CONSIDERATIONS FROM GABRIEL GARCÍA MÁRQUEZ

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7178482

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Abstract : This article aims to discuss the memorialistic element and its consequences for the understanding of the plot of *Memory of my sad whores* (2006), by the Colombian author Gabriel García Márquez. The work, while discussing issues about the heart of human existence, such as the crisis of identity and place in the world that the character brings with him, uses the memory artifact to summarize the events that marked the life of this protagonist and influence his current way of acting. As a methodology, a qualitative research is used, with a bibliographic approach, to analyze social types and their relationships. As a theoretical support, we used the dialogues raised by Halbwachs (2006); Lopes (2014); Ricoeur (2010) among other theorists who articulate the discussion of memory and literature. We can see that it is in the love for the prostitute Delgadina that the old man rediscovers himself in life and in the present, but it is also in the past that part of the plot really becomes clear to the reader, whether due to family traumas or the monotonous years that follow him, reinforcing the importance of structuring the work around the character's self-memory, but adding to that the variant of the forgetting, another point in memory discussions that is fundamental for a more precise interpretation of this corpus.

Keywords : Gabriel Garcia Marquez. memory. Forgetfulness.

INTRODUCTION

Since Ancient Greece, people have studied and preached about the value and importance of memory for the understanding of life, whether in the context of remembering the past for its great deeds, or as a point of study for the improvement of a more complex future. promising, memory has always been considered an extremely valuable artifact for our society. Keeping these memories represents a commitment to the past and to those who lived before us, leaving their contributions and legacy to future generations. It was from this premise of the

memorialistic element as something more than precious, that memory studies in Greek Antiquity took her as a goddess, and through her saw the possibility of re-elaboration of understandings about ancient times as a means of reaching a future. of glories and prosperity, because in the analysis of the past the mistakes of the future would be avoided.

Thus, memory has always occupied and occupies an important part of our lives and its transformation affects the way we see and perceive the world around us. On the other hand, memory failure, forgetting and its variants then came to connote a negative status, and consequently no one wanted to be accused of not remembering something. These were the first moments that the memory lapse takes on a disturbing and inconvenient character. Not only in literature, but in several other areas of knowledge, the topic is an object of study in several fields of knowledge, such as Philosophy, Anthropology, Sociology, History, etc.

Regarding Literary Studies, the relationship between memory and literature is a field of study with countless possibilities, since analyzing the works through the prism of this element makes it possible to recreate spaces, actions, images and new meanings, which in addition to referring to the past and the experiences of the characters, they help us to reread the object of analysis itself, sometimes extremely influenced by this point that drastically changes the direction of the work. Thus, memory is a connecting thread that intertwines the interpretation and understanding of the literary fabric in different ways, after all, with each new memory, new possibilities, like several characters who manage through the memorialistic manifestation to subvert chronological time and enter reminiscences of their lives, a fact that in many narratives is substantial to the literary text, as in the contemporary writing of *Becos da Memória*, by Conceição Evaristo or *Outros cantos*, by Maria Valéria Rezende.

In *Memory of my sad whores* (2006), Gabriel García Márquez, one of the greatest names in world literature, presents us with an unnamed protagonist. A gentleman about to turn ninety years old, who, as a way of marking the passage to almost a century of existence, decides to treat himself to a night of love with a prostitute who was young and, above all, a virgin. In the course of the actions and in the course of the plot, our lord reflects on his existence and the deeds of his life, which he himself does not judge with any value. In this context, the memory of our character is the vehicle that allows the reader to have a close relationship to understand the facts of the plot, since what is told in *Memórias de minhaputas tristes* is seen from the perspective of the memories of our old man and fellow nonagenarian, who, despite being many years old, tells us about his experiences with great description and without notorious traces of forgetfulness, a point that deserves to be questioned and discussed.

From this dreamed and planned night of love, a feeling emerges that will transform this man's life into a new adventure, a fleeting and burning one-sided love story, which will bring him back to the will to live and be happy. The romance with the prostitute and girl Delgadina returns him to a past of happiness and unforgettable memories, which marked the first years of his adult life, but which are also accompanied by memories of trauma and family problems. In this mix of memory, memories and the intertwining of feelings, Márquez builds a quick and accurate narrative like someone who has no time to waste, after all, time is passing fast for everyone, and for our protagonist, even wasting time is a luxury that cannot have.

We start, therefore, from the perspective of analyzing the memorialistic element in this work, understanding how the relationship between the memories of the past and the current life of our character occurs. In reflecting on this idea, we are faced with the premise that the element of memory increasingly constitutes a constituent part of the subjectivity of the character. If the premise that we are our memories is true (BORGES, 1974), it is precisely on this statement that the entire structure that gives the primacy of Memory of my sad whores is centered.

MEMORIES OF A NONAGERNIAN

Individual memory is intrinsically linked to the idea of collective memory. Both instances complement each other, that is, personal memories are built in social interaction and reflect a collective experience of evoking the past. As much as the memories seem unique to us, they are the result of a whole social construction, influenced by all those around us. In this way, memories support each other and live within the social environment of which we are a part, often enabling the difficult understanding of what is collective and what is individual.

As Maurice Halbwachs points out, about memory, “the initial content of these memories, which sets them apart from all the others and would be explained by the fact that they are at the point where two or more series of thoughts intersect, through which they are linked to so many other different groups”. (HALBWACHS, 2006 p. 48) We can, therefore, infer that our memories are the result of the memory of others, who end up living in us, becoming fundamental pieces in a delicate and important game of remembrance and meaning that we attribute to things. The act of remembering becomes an action that interconnects the collective and the individual, reaffirming that a uniquely individual memory would not be possible for social individuals, as we are.

In the analyzed work, the character's individual memory is the novel's narrative configuration, which leads the reader to all the facts, told from the memories, the present itself presents itself in connection with the remembered past in the character's voice, this is shown in the plot from everyday and simplistic details to the structuring of experiences, which happened in the past, reverberate through the character's present.

I live in a colonial house on the sunny pavement of San Nicolas, where I spent all the days of my life without a wife or fortune, where my parents lived and died, and where I proposed to die alone, in the same bed I was born in and on a day that distant and painless desire. My father bought the house at a public auction in the late 19th century, rented the downstairs to luxury stores from a consortium of Italians and set aside this second floor to be happy with the daughter of one of them [...] my mother. MARQUEZ, 2006, p. 09)

In the memory that is told to us above, it is interesting to notice that the past is told with a tone of nostalgic feelings that draws attention, the process of remembering and telling the reader by the narrator is similar to a conversation. From there, we perceive in the reading of the work a tone that borders on the writing of a testimony, because while even the character presents himself in the present time, it is through the understanding and attention to the past that we know his story and enter into his true self, thus guaranteeing us a confessional character to the plot.

This is due to the configuration of the textual genre itself, since “testimony would mean presenting the seen, what happened and this presentation seeks not to forget the fact. The experience presented in the testimonial literature seeks not to be forgotten” (REIS, 2021, p. 255). García Marquez encourages us to get to know this man through his past, through his memory, through his memories and reminiscences of it. In the memory of his work as a columnist for the newspaper we see:

The only thing that remained the same was my newspaper chronicles. The new generations attacked them, as against a mummy of the past that must be demolished, but I kept them in the same tone, without concessions, against the airs of renewal. I was deaf to everything. It was forty years old, but the editors called it the Column of Mudarra the Bastard. (MARQUEZ, 2006, p. 45)

In *Memory of my sad whores*, the family memory, directly related to the feelings and memories of loved ones that accompany us intimately on our journey, makes the reading of the novel an important record about the life of the ninety-year-old man. Considering that it is in this context that those who are part of our first chain of construction of collective memory fall, we know that it is through these people that we learn from an early age the notions of life in a

simpler social group to where more particular reminiscences are processed. and reserved, directly related to everyday spaces, objects and situations. The ninety-year-old man remembers his family with a lot of nostalgia, especially his mother, with nostalgia for what he lived in his youth. The character's memories are combined with a traumatic tone that is possibly supported by the loss of her mother to health problems and then the loss of her father. According to Marquez:

I had been a spoiled child with a multi-gifted mother, annihilated by consumption at the age of fifty, and with a formalistic father whose fault was never known, and who woke up dead in his widower's bed the day the treaty was signed. Neerlandia, which put an end to the Thousand Days War and to so many civil wars of the previous century. (MÁRQUEZ, 2006, p. 16).

According to Halbwachs (2006, p. 81-82), "family memory is a collective construction, a stream of continuous thought [...] that retains from the past only what is alive or capable of living in the consciousness of the group that keeps". This happens because our memories walk in unison in the course of our family's life, they are never taken in an isolated context, but in sharing with those who are also part of us, the first social group to which we belong and which we mirror ourselves as the first behavior examples.

As he never formed a blood family from a relationship that gave him children, what remains for our character are the memories, perhaps these being his only heirs. Added to this, the objects and jewelry that the mother left, as well as the impeccable teachings and morals of the father as an example of posture and behavior, constituting artifacts and lessons that he will carry with him throughout his journey. His only family was the set of prostitutes he'd been involved with all his life. As he said himself, "he never even slept with a woman without paying". (MARQUEZ, 2006, p. 24). And these were many.

You claim to have never really loved any woman other than your mother, meeting Delgadina is as if you knew the feeling for the first time. In his memoir description, we see that the feeling now celebrated in his chest works as an elixir of youth for this man. In a new tone of life, the character finds light and reasons to live, as the experimentation of passion and the whirlwind of feelings for the young prostitute rejuvenate him to a world of possibilities that was not seen before. Thus, this old gentleman never tires of reaffirming how he is changed with the emergence of this passion. In one of the most exquisite parts of the work, García shows us:

Thanks to her, I faced my natural self for the first time while I was ninety years old. I discovered that my obsession with every thing in its place, every subject in its time, every word in its style, was not the deserved prize of an orderly

mind, but, on the contrary, a whole system of simulation invented by me to hide the disorder of my nature. I discovered that I am not disciplined out of virtue, but as a denial of my neglect; that I seem generous to cover up my pettiness, that I pretend to be prudent when in fact I am suspicious and always think the worst, that I am conciliatory so as not to succumb to my repressed cramps, that I am only punctual so that no one knows how little time matters to me oblivious. I finally discovered that love is not a state of the soul, but a sign of the zodiac. (MARQUEZ, 2006, p. 74)

Thanks to the feelings he has for the young Delgadina, man rediscovers himself, sees himself as a real human being, full of insecurities, imperfections and dilemmas, which makes all his variety of certainties and finished positions about what, until then he had believed it to be true in his life. In his love for the prostitute, which here symbolically represents his ninety-year gift, he gains much more than a night of pleasure.

Our character is accompanied by the whores, a few co-workers, the books he inherited from his father's collection and the faithful maid, who has always accompanied him. We come across an extremely lonely person who finds in carnal pleasure an escape from the hard days that pass through his existence. It should be noted that the character of the work in question emphasizes a strong attachment to memories as a way out of a painful present, that is, the breath for the sadness of the present is found in the happy memories that work here as a mitigating factor for the current condition.

In this way, we walk through the memories of this gentleman in the most varied instances of his life. Work, family, short relationships that didn't work out, fear of loneliness, the passion for the unknown whore, the mediocre life attributed to her. All the terrain on which the reader steps is centered on the plane of memory.

A fact that sharpens an important analysis to conjecture would be about the veracity of such memories. When dealing with a nonagenarian man, it is feared that the variant of forgetting may permeate these memories, after all, it would not be surprising that memories of the past could be compromised for a man who is approaching his centenary of life, according to Ricoeur:

In fact, what forgetting awakens at this crossroads is the aporia itself at the source of the problematic character of the representation of the past, namely, the unreliability of memory. Forgetting is the challenge par excellence opposed to the ambition of memory's reliability. (RICOEUR, 2010, p. 425).

The protagonist fears losing her memory and the fear of this haunts her. What would you be without the memories? Losing one's memory would be like something extremely painful, as it implies the suppression of an important part of oneself. The character of oblivion

in the work is given to the character in the anguish of being overcome by the past, of witnessing the search for memories and not finding them. Realizing that he is ninety years old, comes the fear of memory loss. If this man presents his life to the reader purely and solely through his memories, what would his life be without them?

In the fifth decade I had begun to imagine what old age was when I noticed the first holes in my memory. I rummaged around the house looking for my glasses until I found I was wearing them, or got into the shower with them, or put on my reading glasses without taking my eyes off. One day I had breakfast twice because I forgot the first one, and I learned to recognize my friends' alarm when they didn't dare remind me that I was telling the same story I had told the week before. At that time, I had in my memory a list of familiar faces and another with the names of each one, but at the time of greeting I couldn't get the faces to match the names. (MÁRQUEZ, 2006, p. 14).

Forgetting, however, also has a positive, even liberating, character. In this way, what would our life be if we kept absolutely everything that affects us, positively or negatively. Forgetting is liberating as it leaves us free for the next experiences and experiences. In view of this, “in the absence of any possibility of making oneself understood, silence about oneself - different from oblivion - may even be a necessary condition.” (POLLAK, 1989, p. 07). Thus, carrying the weight of not forgetting would be a very painful burden for our shoulders and minds, because without this unfolding of memory, the subject would be linked to all types of memory, whether happy or traumatic events. Understanding this prism of understanding the process of forgetting in two possibilities: one with a sad and painful tone, and another as happy and liberating, we see that

When talking about the centrality of forgetting in Benjamin's philosophy, Gagnebin highlights the fact that for the German thinker, as well as for Nietzsche, the exercise of writing history should be carried out rejecting all historicist logic that always intends to talk about the past through a pretense of objectivity carried to exhaustion, which for the philosopher of Sils-Maria would be the repulsive gesture of antiquarian history (NIETZSCHE, 2003). In this sense, both Benjamin and Nietzsche make us think of a “plastic force of forgetting” (NIETZSCHE, 2003, p. 10), that is, a need to ruminate on the past that has a beginning time, but also a moment of detachment, the which in no way means denying the past, but only knowing how to incorporate it in an affirmative way into life. In the same essay, Gagnebin speaks of “happy oblivion”, articulating this oblivion to the image of the sick child who “calms down little by little thanks to the hands that caress and the voice that tells a story, thus tracing the river of pain into a bed that it will lead to 'the sea of happy oblivion'” (GAGNEBIN, 2015, p. 11). Happy oblivion would be the opposite of the pure gesture of denying what happened, of not thinking about or not elaborating on the past. (LOPES, 2014, p. 24-25)

Thus, the concreteness of oblivion caused by age would be a fact of no return, a condition that, no matter how long it took, could not escape. The importance of incorporating forgetting into life, starts from the premise that we can free ourselves from traumatic facts and memories, and that without this mnemonic device, our lives would be trapped in a terrible painful carousel of present and past. After all, “articulating the past historically does not mean 'recognising it as it was'. It means taking possession of a memory when it appears like a flash in a moment of danger” (BENJAMIN, 2010, p. 11). For the character, the plot of oblivion surrounded him in small gestures, it was in the small actions of everyday life that he presented himself as a clash that was avoided, but that was always waiting for the confrontation. We can see in the words of García Marquez,

One day I had breakfast twice, because I had forgotten the first one, and I learned to recognize my friends' alarm when they dared not remind me that I was telling the same story I had told the week before. At that time, I had in my memory a list of familiar faces and another with the names of each one, but at the time of greeting I couldn't get the faces to coincide with the names. (MARQUEZ, 2006, p. 14)

The work also understands the spatial instance as a strong element that acts on memories, since important scenarios are brought to the unfolding of facts and actions, as they work sometimes as triggers, sometimes as a background for the narrative of *Memory of my sad whores*. Once these spaces are understood, as social representations of stories and events that focus on memories, the plot develops in several spaces that provide the remembrance of scenes from the past, making the protagonist reflect the condition of a lord at the age of ninety who considers himself of mission accomplished, and with a not so prosperous life.

Thus, the house, the newspaper where he worked, as well as other spaces in the city he frequented, are listed in this category. But above all, prostitution brothels stand out, of which he had been a regular customer throughout his life. These spaces, some of them for pleasure, were the complement of his house for many years and keep significant parts of his life and history. As we see in the work:

On one of those uncertain days I ended up in the very noble Rua dos Notarios, and was surprised to find nothing but the rubble of the old hotel for fleeting encounters where I was forcibly initiated into the arts of love shortly before I was eleven years old. It had been a mansion of former shipowners, splendid like few in the city, with alabaster columns and tinsel friezes. At the age of twelve, still in my elementary school shorts and boots, I could not resist the temptation to explore the upper floors while my father struggled

in one of his interminable meetings, and I was met with a heavenly spectacle.
. (MÁRQUEZ, 2006, p. 121).

In this passage we can see the moment when the character was introduced to the world of brothels, becoming, since then, a regular customer of the place and making it the extension of his house, considering how significant the experience in these spaces was for our Mr. In this way, time passed and only the brothels with the “oldest profession in the world” remained as a stronghold of pleasure for the young man who sought to have fun with the bodies of prostitutes. As the narrative unfolds, we understand these spaces as environments that metaphorize all the pleasure of a life and that portray the condition of a man who never had anyone. As he himself says: “I never slept with any woman without paying.” (MARQUEZ, 2006, p. 36).

Thus, places of memory are devices that show us the importance of spaces for our life and remembrance, as they carry with them the experiences that constitute us as social subjects and belonging to a group. There are houses, schools, businesses, tourist spots, all these locations can be significant for remembrance and activation of memories, from the most positively affective, to spaces of rancor or other negative feelings. The most famous of these environments is our house, but other specific places can also assume this function, as they are assigned the values necessary to occupy this category. This is what happens to the character in the novel. As Nora explains:

[...] if we still inhabited our memory, we would not need to dedicate places to it. There would be no places because there would be no memory transported by history. Each gesture, even the most everyday, would be lived as a religious repetition of what has always been done, in a carnal identification of the act and the meaning. As long as there is a trace, distance, mediation, we are no longer within true memory, but within history. (NORA, 1993, p. 8-9).

This implication is based on the assumption that we do not only build individual memories, that is, our memories are always supported by those of other people with whom we live. Thus, we could not speak of places that are uniquely ours, since it is within sociability that we give meaning to many spatial instances. All these settings arouse the most diverse memories of the subjects we live with and serve as a trigger for the remembrance of a shared and socially experienced past. In this way, for the protagonist, these brothels represent the course of a chronological life and how it walked up to the moment it is today.

Furthermore, the protagonist keeps her memories as a treasure in a palace, a guarantee of a lucidity not weakened by chronological time and the devastating passing of her days and years. In his love for Delgadina, the young prostitute, the old man finds the strength he needs

to resist as long as necessary, stating that he would “support himself in this and not give in to the years. With the strength of the memories accumulated on the already long road of existence, I would build many more. After all, his time had not yet come.” (MÁRQUEZ, 2006, p. 119)

Linking himself to the spaces, the narrator presents us with objects that help in evoking memories for the nonagenarian lord. These memory objects are most often furniture, personal items, gifts from friends or loved ones, which act as triggers for the mnemonic process. Through these objects memories, personalities and episodes that were part of our journey are evoked. In turn, such artifacts are configured as a material reservoir of our memories, always at hand and capable of referring us to the past. In *Memory of my sad whores*, the protagonist maintains an affective relationship with the old objects in the house, capable of making him evoke memories of the family, as follows:

Unlike the other furniture, and myself, the table on which I write seems to be in better health with the passage of time, because it was made of noble woods by my paternal grandfather, who was a ship's carpenter. Even when I don't have to write, every morning I set the table with the idle rigor that has made me lose so many loves. (MÁRQUEZ, 2006, p. 38).

In this excerpt, we see that the table, always present, makes him evoke the memories of his grandfather. The disciplined arrangement of the furniture is partly the result of the traditional creation passed on by the family, which explains why the table is always impeccable. In other moments of the novel, there is mention of the jewels left by the mother, because in addition to their financial value, they are very significant objects of memory, since they were for the personal use of the matriarch, who loved and kept them with immense esteem and appreciation, the jewels serve as a link between the protagonist and the memories of the deceased mother, having the sentimental and symbolic value of true amulets.

We understand that what constitutes the material leftover of the matriarch's memories are just these jewels, which configure the portal between the now and the memory of life with her mother. The character who makes no mention of any other family members lives in this mausoleum of memories, full of objects from his family's past and from his own life, making this space a temple to the past, a true home museum that carries the ghost of a time that would never return. According to Flávio Leonel Abreu da Silveira and Manuel Ferreira Lima Filho:

It is exactly these different senses that objects have that allow them the ability to evoke memories and experience the tension between forgetfulness and memories, from the contact with the materiality of the thing and the possible meanings that it carries with it. (SILVEIRA; LIMA FILHO, 2005, p. 38).

The use of objects as mnemonic receptacles only highlights the plural character of the memorialistic element that lives in different planes and instances of our life. The gentleman who had found love at the age of ninety in the arms of a young prostitute not only presents his experiences and experiences through his memory, but uses it as a mental exercise to preserve his lucidity and scare away the danger of oblivion that becomes threatening. In this way, knowing someone's memories is a true process of personal undressing, it is done by entering the most secret recesses of each personality and subjectivity that makes up the human being in question.

In the plot of *Memory of my sad whores* , knowing the past of the nonagenarian man and protagonist of the story is to reveal a little of the subjectivity that is behind each lifestyle and attitude that accompanies him in the present. From the traumas of the past, the fear of the uncertainty of the future and the fear of loneliness in death, in the fabric of the telling of these memories, the writing of the unfolding of the now for our lord is made.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In *Memory of my sad whores* , the plot focuses on the story of life by the protagonist himself, as well as on the facts of how life is changed when he finds his first love, at the age of ninety. The narrative of the work weaves a handful of actions that make us cheer for the victory of love in the face of adversity that the difference of age and social realities could raise. Furthermore, all this is remembered by the memories of the nonagenarian who finds freedom from the prison of a tiny life when he falls madly in love with the young prostitute Delgadina.

An album of memories is presented to us as we enter the pages of the novel, and the memorial element is not only the mark of the work, but the whole of it. Thus, the memorialistic intertwining is the spice that makes the plot more intriguing and captivating, because through the act of remembering, you bring us the account of your experiences, sometimes supported by age and experience, inferring that those who have many memories might have carries with it the burden of living for many years.

Living ninety years for some may seem like a very heavy burden, for the protagonist it is just another step to be accomplished or another obstacle to be overcome. From the analysis of memory in the novel, it is possible to know the feelings, frustrations, pains and sensations of the character who, at ninety years of age, experiences a feeling never felt before. With the fragments of life that make time go by beyond the days, we understand that García Márquez

doesn't just introduce us to a man who wants to mark his ninety years by revolutionizing his routine by sleeping with a nymphet, he wants to be reborn that night, to return to the life of an existence from which for many he would already be dead. It is in the need of this unbridled love that the omniscient narrator shows us the overflow of feelings.

The character's voice walks in a mix of feelings and description of actions that range from the happiness of meeting the loved one to the sadness of the non-concrete relationship, as a result of a tragedy in the brothel. The unveiling of these memories and the fear of oblivion are not just the confession of a fragile human being who keeps secrets with him and needed to vent, it is clearly the revelation of the subjective character of the lord himself, who, mixing the voice of the narrator, tells his adventures helping us to understand who your person truly is.

When he shows himself to be weak in the face of the feelings that come to his mind because of the memory of his beloved, it is, in fact, that the old man shows himself to be strong, because he now understood that “the truth is that I could not stand my soul and began to become aware of old age. for my weaknesses in the face of love” (MARQUEZ, 2006, p. 97). The plot uses memory as a background that highlights the facts, leading us to root for the character and endorse any character deviations or bad behavior that he presents or has already presented. Understanding only love as the only tool of release for an empty soul, loving for the first time, deeply, truly and intensely was the key that unlocked the character's sad life.

If García Marquez only grants this key to the ninety years of our lord, perhaps the real gift was not the night of love, but the liberation for everything that still has to be lived, now with an open soul, a beating heart and the happy mind. Too late? Maybe not! In *Memory of my sad whores*, each moment may be your last, but above all, each moment is a new memory that sinks into the depths of your soul and somehow echoes all the unfolding of what lies ahead.

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